

The Development of the Contextual Network Project: Designing for Sustainable Development in a Remote Mexican Community

Mario A Moreno Rocha, Carlos A Martínez Sandoval

¹UsaLab Laboratorio de Usabilidad, Universidad Tecnológica de la Mixteca
Huajuapán de León, Oaxaca, 69000, Mexico and SACHI, University of St Andrews, St Andrews
KY16 9AJ, Fife, Scotland, UK

ABSTRACT

The present work portrays the development and results of the project named Contextual Network, carried out in the community of Santos Reyes Yucuná, in Oaxaca, Mexico. A contextual study was elaborated and subsequently, a usability study of a prototype in development was made for a system that would benefit the women in this marginalised community. In this work important findings are shown relating to the users' disposition toward the use of new technologies; in addition to the way to approach them and a correct form to introduce technology for the benefit of such communities.

Keywords: Contextual Studies, usability, marginalised communities, touch technology, Wizard of Oz tests.

1. INTRODUCTION

We like to think about technology as a magic bullet, one that could solve every little problem around us efficiently and with ease. As we all know, unfortunately, this is not the case, although in our field of research technology might get us closer to a solution, or at least, allow us to have a better understanding of the problem (Carta a la Tía Ofelia, 2009).

This is particularly true when working with indigenous communities and their more important challenges. A complex and sizable number of issues have to be taken into consideration in order to completely understand and try to develop a useful solution for them. Then, technology could be turned into an instant equaliser, allowing them to reach out and seize opportunities otherwise unobtainable to them.

This is the case with the women of the remote community of Santos Reyes Yucuná, in the Southern Mexican State of Oaxaca. Located in the Mixtec Region, Yucuná is one of the poorest areas in one of the least developed states in Mexico. It is a small town of about two thousand inhabitants, mainly women. This is the origin of large migration into the United States, in which men travel north of the border in order to work for a better life and to support the family they leave behind.

For generations, women in Santos Reyes Yucuná have been getting married early in life so they can have a large family (on average, around six children). Their rationale is that having many children can lead to higher income for the whole family. Many women take their children with them to larger cities, mainly in the more affluent North of Mexico, so they can beg for money on the streets. As this happens, children do not attend school regularly. When the family collects enough money, they return to their community until all the money is spent, only to go back to the streets the next year, perpetuating the cycle of poverty and marginalisation (Cuéntamelo Todo, 2011).

Several other challenges in this community include low literacy levels. Although the women are bilingual (Mixtec and/or Spanish), few of them can read or write, with older women having difficulty communicating in Spanish. As expected, they also have little exposure to computer technologies.

2. THE SIFE-UTM STUDENT TEAM AND ITA-VIKO

Santos Reyes Yucuná is about four hours away from our university, the Universidad Tecnológica de la Mixteca, (UTM), a state-run technological university located in the same Mixtec Region in Oaxaca. The town first came into our attention through the “*Promoción al Desarrollo*” brigade (literally “development promotion”) which leave our university

every day at dawn. They bring veterinary and health expertise to remote localities, which couldn't get it otherwise. They are university technicians and professors specially trained to help families and their animals, and to teach them how to get purified water, restore main roads, and set up communications, among other activities.

During the year 2009, the brigade contacted our SIFE-UTM university student team. Formerly SIFE, Enactus is an international non-profit organisation which brings together students, academics and business leaders committed to use the power of entrepreneurial action to improve the quality of lives and the standard of living for people in need. There are 70 (SIFE) Enactus teams in Mexican universities, and our SIFE-UTM team is the proud tetra Mexican champions in the national championships.

UTM advisors, professors, and students visited Santos Reyes Yucuná and realised that, before any technology solutions could be designed, hearts and minds had to be won. The first activity conducted in the town was a human development workshop that the women of Yucuná attended reluctantly. Among the workshop findings were that the women thought of themselves as worthless, they all had very low self-esteem.

The SIFE-UTM team created a business model in which they analysed the women's context in order to determine which productive project could be taken into consideration. The team couldn't find any natural resources in the area except for cornhusks, the remains of maize, which they used to feed donkeys. With cornhusks as raw materials, the UTM team came up with an idea to create flowers that the women of Yucuná could assemble and sell.

The project grew with great expectations. In two months the women created their own brand, "Ita-Viko" (pretty woman in Mixtec) and more women got involved in the process. The university team provided training on entrepreneurial skills and business savvy through human development workshops.

Ita-Viko has proved to be a successful business venture. In their first year they managed to export their flowers and during the second year they diversified their offering, selling earrings, necklaces and rings, all made of cornhusks. Ita-Viko created a real alternative to the only way of life the people of Santos Reyes Yucuná had known for decades.

3. THE SIFE-UTM TEAM LEAVES

By SIFE (Enactus) bylaws, university teams have to leave the projects in which they participate. This meant that the students and professors had to stop coming regularly into the community to teach the women how to create new products, how to set prices, how to sell products online, and eventually stop teaching them about human development.

Further communication among the team and Ita-Viko was allowed, but SIFE-UTM couldn't keep visiting them on a regular basis. So, the predicament to be solved by means of our project was born: How could we support the women of Ita-Viko without the regular help and presence of the SIFE-UTM team?

4. OUR ROLE IN THE PROJECT

Carlos Alberto Martínez, the article's co-author, was at the time Vice President of the SIFE-UTM team. Also, he worked at the UsaLab Laboratorio de Usabilidad in our same university. UsaLab is a usability laboratory founded in 2002, intended to support HCI research in our university. Since 2006, we have offered services to industry as well. It is staffed by professors and students, some of them past winners at the ACM Student Design Competition at CHI, CLIHC (the Latin American HCI conferences) and MexIHC (the Mexican HCI conference).

The challenge of SIFE leaving Ita-Viko came to our attention. Our first instinct and response were to solve the problem by means of technology, but a bigger question was then formulated: Was technology a way to reduce, minimise and support the lack of communication among teams, even if the women of Ita-Viko couldn't read or write Spanish, let alone know how to use a computer? (Crespo García, 2008), (Harindranath and Sein, 2007).

In particular, based on SIFE-UTM's work with the women, we identified the basic tasks that the system should accomplish:

- a) Presentation of job training videos: users wanted to continue their practice and job training, this time from a distance through instructional videos teaching them how to create new products.
- b) Presentation of business training videos: an extremely important part for new members and to consolidate Ita-Viko as a company.

- c) Direct communication with the SIFE-UTM team: to address questions and maintain their connection to the team.

To address this challenge we set out to complete the following three steps, following a user-centered approach: A) A preliminary ethnographic study, to understand the women's environment, context and their approach to technology; B) In situ testing of graphic prototypes for system icons and options to assure a complete understanding for the system's options; and finally, C) A Wizard of Oz testing for high fidelity prototypes.

4.1 Ethnographic Study

We observed the women in the contexts in which they would use the technology. This occurred in two locations, Santos Reyes Yucuná, and in the city of Oaxaca (to observe the users making use of technology similar to that which would be implemented in the project and that we could not carry to the community).

As a tight-knit community, Santos Reyes Yucuná does not accept outsiders with ease. So, we approached them with the help of the SIFE-UTM team and with the help of an interpreter. As expected, the barriers eventually came down and we were accepted as honorary members of the community. This is not to be taken lightly, as they did not embrace us until they were confident that we didn't pose any danger or conflict to their interests, customs, and traditions.

4.2 Observations in the Palacio del Gobierno de Oaxaca Museum

With the objective of testing a larger number of technologies and observing their interaction, we asked users to use six devices with particular characteristics (e.g., headphones, interactive videos, tablets, trackballs, etc.). We achieve this at a museum in the city of Oaxaca (the Oaxacan Government Palace Museum). Again, the results were a joyful reception by the users (ict4d, 2011). They shared headphones, toyed with the interactive tablets, and finally accepted technology as a way in which they could learn, have fun, and have a presence in this new Ita-Viko phase.

4.3 Ethnographic Study Results

Based on our observations and subsequent interviews we learned that the women could use and appreciate technology (e.g., televisions, mobile phones), although they don't have experience with tablets or large interactive displays, they welcome them (del Álamo, 2010). Also, they could learn through training videos,

they prefer a tabletop to a vertical display for interactions, and they all have difficulty using technologies that require reading or writing.

4.4 Design and Usability Testing

We developed two designs of the system and obtained feedback from users in the community through the use of an iPad (see Figure 1, below). This was useful for us to gain feedback on the visual design and allowed us to correct issues that led us to our final prototype. The final design was tested using a Wizard of Oz setup in which one of us performed the functions of the computer. Due to the fact that our end goal was to use an interactive tabletop display, as we didn't have access to one, we used a 40" Samsung LCD, Full HD 1080p screen connected to a Windows 7 laptop instead. We asked the users (in groups of three or four, depending on the previously considered demographic characteristics) to make use of the equipment. One of us would see where the users interacted and operated the software from the laptop. We conducted the tests at Santos Reyes Yucuná's communal lounge.

Figure 1. Users interacting with and iPad in the community of Santos Reyes Yucuná. She received an explanation with a printed magazine to show her how to use it.

Once again, with the help of an interpreter, we conducted two tests using a Think Aloud Protocol as well as two other tests using the Co-discovery method. We noticed that the second method was way more useful. After the tests, we conducted a final Focus Group to obtain further opinions.

The following images show the development of these tests and the prototype evaluated. See the following Figure 2.

Figure 2. An user-group evaluation of the prototype through a Wizard of Oz method in their community centre. The technology was accepted immediately.

3. NOT A CONCLUSION

Based on our testing, the prototype worked quite well and was very close to solving user needs. The next challenge is implementing a final product and delivering it in a way that is sustainable and could support the continued growth and independence of the community. Currently, we are in search of additional funding to continue this project.

Developing projects for marginalised communities, and consequently, managing to directly assist them, has always been the primary interest of our university, and therefore, of our laboratory. For this reason, our participation in this project has brought us great joy, not only because of the technology we developed, but due to the fact that the project aims to serve a remote community in Oaxaca

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We profoundly thank the women of the Ita-Viko project from the community Santos Reyes Yucuná, as well as all the Mexican Science Council, Conacyt, the Red TIC of academic researchers, the members of the SIFE-UTM (Enactus) student team, the UsaLab Laboratorio de Usabilidad and our software development company, KadaSoftware, all of them participants in this project. Special thanks to our Universidad Tecnológica de la Mixteca.